

Paper Electrophoretic Separation and Estimation of the Constituents of Pyrolusite and Indian Coin (Cupro-nickel)[†]

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The separation of the main constituents of pyrolusite and Indian coin paper electrophoretically under a potential gradient of 2.2 volts/cm using 0.1 M sodium acetate and 0.1 M sodium formate as carrier electrolyte on Whatman Paper No. 1 (3 cm × 40 cm) shows that iron and manganese from pyrolusite and copper and nickel from cupro-nickel Indian coin can be successfully separated and determined spectrophotometrically after eluting from the paper. Advantage of this method over existing methods is that separation is possible in 15 min.

SUCCESSFUL separations¹⁻⁴ of Fe(III) from Co(II), Mn(II) and Ni(II); Pb(II) from Co(II) and Mn(II); Bi(III) from Co(II) and Mn(II); Hg(II) from Cu(II), Mn(II) and Co(II); and Cu(II) from Co(II) using 0.1 M sodium acetate solution as supporting electrolyte, and Cu(II) from Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II); Fe(III) from Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II) using 0.1 M sodium formate solution as supporting electrolyte by paper electrophoresis have been achieved. This prompted us to attempt an analysis of pyrolusite and Indian coin (cupro-nickel) by paper electrophoresis and a subsequent estimation of Fe, Mn and Cu, Ni.

Ore analysis :

Preparation of migrant solution (pyrolusite)⁵⁻⁶ : Pyrolusite (0.4987 g) was decomposed by 15 ml conc. HCl by evaporating to almost dryness. 15 ml dil. HCl (1 : 1) was added, heated to dissolve the residue and evaporated. The soluble residue was dissolved in minimum amount of dil. HCl. The solution was filtered in a 50 ml volumetric flask. The volume of the solution was made up with dil. HCl.

Paper electrophoresis of the migrant : A drop of pyrolusite solution (1.2×10^{-4} g) having iron and manganese as the main constituents was electrophorised using 0.1 N sodium acetate as the supporting electrolyte. Apparatus used for the separation of iron and manganese of pyrolusite was a Durrum's type vertical electrophoretic instrument. Paper strips (3 cm × 40 cm) from Whatman No. 1 were used as the supporting medium, 800 volt applied and the paper strip was taken out after 15 min run and dried. The zones of the migrants were identified with the help of specific reagent, potassium ferrocyanide for iron and 3 N potassium hydroxide solution for manganese.

It was found that clean separation of iron and manganese was possible. Separation sequences and position of migrating zone from the point of

application after 15 min run is shown in Table 1, where '+' sign indicates migration towards the anode and '-' sign towards the cathode.

Migrant	Separation sequences of the migrant and the distance traversed by the zone in cm	
	Iron	Manganese
Pyrolusite	+0.9 to -0.3	-1.9 to -2.7

Estimation of iron and manganese : After electrophoresis, the electrophoregram was dried and the portions of the strip containing iron and manganese were cut out from it after matching the said portions against the stained marked strip.

Iron (direct method) : The region of the strip containing iron was treated with 2 N HCl and evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was treated with 0.8 N H₂SO₄, warmed and filtered into a 25 ml measuring flask. A little of 0.8 N H₂SO₄ was added and washings of the strips were poured into the measuring flask. The volume was made up to the mark with 0.8 N H₂SO₄.

A blank solution was prepared taking the same paper strip of identical dimension, having no iron, which was treated with 2 N HCl and 0.8 N H₂SO₄ as before.

The optical density of the eluted iron was measured against this blank at the wave length of 305 m μ and found to be 0.012.

In this method, the amount of iron present in pyrolusite was calculated using the equation

$$C = \frac{O.D.}{\epsilon} = \frac{\text{Optical density}}{\text{Extinction co-efficient}}$$

C = Concentration in molarity
 $\epsilon = 21807^{-8}$.

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Manganese (KIO₄ method): Portion of the electrophoregram containing manganese was treated with 2 N H₂SO₄ and manganese was extracted in the same way as iron. To this eluted solution, 5 ml 85% H₃PO₄, 20 mg AgNO₃ and 0.15 g potassium meta-periodate were added; heated to boiling with stirring and kept at slightly below the boiling point for 1 hr. It was cooled and diluted to 50 ml in a volumetric flask.

The blank solution was prepared, as in the case of iron and similarly treated with H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄, AgNO₃ and KIO₄. The optical density of the eluted manganese solution was measured against this blank solution at 525 mμ and found to be 0.04.

A standard solution of manganous sulphate was prepared and a calibration curve for manganese was drawn from which the concentration of this eluted solution was calculated.

The percentages of iron and manganese in pyrolusite were calculated as given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Constituents in pyrolusite as oxide	Optical densities of the eluted solutions after separation by paper electrophoresis	Concentration of the eluted solutions calculated from spectrophotometric method in terms of Fe and Mn in g/lit.	Percentage of Fe and Mn calculated from molar concentration, volume of migrants, volume of diluents and weight of pyrolusite taken	Actual % of the constituents as Fe and Mn calculated by standard method
Fe	0.012	3 × 10 ⁻³	6.17%	6.44%
Mn	0.04	11.60 × 10 ⁻³	48.45%	53.26%

Standard methods for estimation of iron and manganese: Iron and manganese were estimated titrimetrically using standard dichromate as usual.

Alloy analysis:

Preparation of Indian coin solution: The coin (2.4937 g) was taken in a conical flask and 10 ml conc. HNO₃ was added. It was then heated and allowed to react till all the alloy dissolved. The solution was diluted with water, 0.5 g urea added and heated nearly to boiling to decompose the nitrous fumes. The solution was transferred quantitatively into a 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with water.

Experimental procedure: Quantitative separation of the constituents of coin was possible electrophoretically using 0.1 M sodium formate as carrier electrolyte. The vertical apparatus was used for the paper electrophoretic separation of the main constituents of the coin solution. Potential gradient of 2.2 volts/cm for 3 hr run was maintained. After electrophoresis the electrophoregram was dried and developed carefully avoiding spreading of the zones. The electrophoregram was developed with yellow ammonium sulphide. A brown band for Cu(II) and a black one for Ni(II) were located and an attempt was made to estimate copper and nickel from the band spectrophotometrically.

The separation of the principal constituents (copper and nickel) is shown in Table 3, where '+' stands for anionic movement and '-' for cationic movement. The solution used for separation was 0.004 ml.

TABLE 3—CARRIER ELECTROLYTE 0.1 M SODIUM FORMATE

Migrant	Separation sequences of the migrant and the distance traversed by the zone in cm	
	Copper	Nickel
Coin	-0.8 to -1.9	-3.3 to -5.3

Estimation of copper ("Neo-cuproin" method): After electrophoresis, the electrophoregram was dried and the portion of the strip containing copper was cut out from the electrophoregram after matching the said portion against the stained marked strip.

The region of the strip containing copper was treated with 2 N H₂SO₄ and copper was extracted as in the case of iron. Total volume was 15 ml. From the extracted solution 5 ml was taken. To the 5 ml solution in a separatory funnel, 5 ml of 10% hydroxyl-ammonium chloride solution to reduce Cu(II) to Cu(I) and 5 ml of a 30% sodium citrate solution to complex any other metals present, were added. Ammonia solution was then added for adjustment of the pH to about 4 (with congored paper), followed by 5 ml of 0.1% solution of "neocuproin" (2,9-methyl-1,10-phenanthroline) in absolute ethanol. It was shaken for about 30 sec with 5 ml of chloroform and the layers were allowed to separate. A further extraction with 2.5 ml of chloroform was carried out. The optical density at 457 mμ against a reagent blank was measured and found to be 0.575.

A standard solution of copper sulphate was prepared and a calibration curve for copper was drawn from which the extinction coefficient of copper was calculated.

Using this extinction co-efficient the concentration of copper in the eluted solution was calculated. The percentage of copper in coin (25 paise) was then calculated as given in Table 4.

TABLE 4

Optical densities of the eluted solution after separation by paper electrophoresis	Concentration of the eluted solution calculated from spectrophotometric method in terms of Cu and Ni in g mole/lit	Percentage of Cu and Ni calculated from molar concentration, volume of migrant, volume of diluents and weight of coin taken	Actual % of Cu and Ni calculated by standard method analysis
Cu	0.75	7.56 × 10 ⁻³	72%
Ni	0.009	0.95 × 10 ⁻³	26.1%
			74.2% 26.3%

Estimation of nickel (dimethylglyoxime method): The region of the strip containing nickel was treated with 2 N H₂SO₄ and nickel was extracted in

the usual procedure. The extracted volume of nickel solution was 10 ml. The solution was taken in a 50 ml volumetric flask. To 10 ml of the solution 5 ml of 10% citric acid solution was added and neutralised with ammonia, a few drops of which was added in excess ($pH > 7.5$). Then 3 ml of 1% dimethyl glyoxime in ethanol was added. The solution was extracted with three 3 ml portion of chloroform, shaking for 30 sec each time. The combined chloroform was shaken with 6 ml of 0.5 M ammonia (1 : 30). The ammonia washing was shaken with 2 ml of chloroform and the latter was added to the main chloroform extract. The nickel was returned to the ionic state by shaking the chloroform extract vigorously for 1 min with two 5 ml portions of 0.5 M HCl. The HCl solution was transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask, diluted to about 50 ml, 1 ml of saturated Br_2 water added, followed by 2 ml of conc. ammonia. 1 ml of 1% dimethylglyoxime solution was added and diluted up to the mark. After 5 min the optical density at 445 $m\mu$ against a blank was measured and found to be 0.009.

A standard solution of nickel sulphate was prepared to obtain a calibration curve for nickel.

The extinction co-efficient of nickel was used to calculate its concentration in the eluted solution. The percentage of nickel in Indian coin (25 paise) was then calculated from the concentration term as shown in Table 4.

Using the equation,

$$O.D. = E.C. \cdot l$$

the extinction co-efficient of copper and nickel were calculated. The extinction co-efficients (E) 0.76×10^4 for copper and 0.094×10^4 for nickel were obtained.

So, the amounts of copper and nickel present in the coin (25 paise) were calculated by the equation,

$$C = \frac{O.D.}{E} \text{ in molarity}$$

Standard method for estimation of copper and nickel: Copper was estimated gravimetrically using ammonium thiocyanate and nickel using dimethylglyoxime as usual.

It can be said from the experimental data that paper electrophoresis technique can equally be applied for analysis of pyrolusite and Indian coin.

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